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A numerical technique for obtaining approximate solutions of the SIV epidemic model

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce a numerical method for solving the well-known propagation model, namely the Susceptible-Infected-Vaccinated (SIV) model based on the Ritz-Galerkin method. This way Legendre orthogonal polynomials and Gauss quadrature formula are utilized to reduce the SIV system of differential equations to the problem of solving algebraic equations. The method is general, easy to implement, and yields very accurate results. Illustrative examples are included to demonstrate the validity and applicability of the technique.

1. Introduction

Infectious diseases have always been an important part of evolution and have had devastating effects on human life and the population [1]. The modeling of infectious diseases is a tool that has been used to study the diseases spread. The

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aim of epidemic modeling is to understand and evaluate strategies in order to control the spread of disease. The first mathematical model to describe epidemics was proposed by Daniel Bernoulli for smallpox in 1760 [2, 3]. In the early 20th century, mathematical methods for epidemiology were first introduced by Ronald Ross, Anderson Gray, Mckendrick and others [4–6]. Mathematical models for controlling the infection, the infection, which is an essential tool in epidemiology studies can be found in [7–9].

There exist two main procedures to construct epidemic models, deterministic and stochastic [10]. In the deterministic approach, the mathematical structure is achieved by the construction and analysis of the epidemic differential equations [10, 11]. While stochastic models are probability structures by consideration of random processes in the differential equations or using the Markov chain [10]. It is necessary for these models to consider vaccination factors. Various mathematical models have been formulated and analyzed in epidemiology [4, 6, 11]. SIV model is one kind of epidemic model to describe the epidemic in a population [4]. Wie proposed a numerical simulation method for the SIV epidemic model with impulsive vaccination and infection-age. His results show that this method is effective and possesses the potential value of the application. Since theoretical analysis is relatively complicated So, the numerical methods may apply to solve some problems of this model [1]. Xue et al. showed that numerous kinds of bifurcation occur for the SIV model [12].

The SIV model with proportional vaccination is formulated as follows [4]:

$$(1) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{dS}{dt} &= \mu - (\mu + k)S - \beta SI + \gamma I, \\ \frac{dI}{dt} &= \beta SI - (\mu + \gamma)I, \\ \frac{dV}{dt} &= kS - \mu V, \end{aligned}$$

$$S(0) = S_0, \quad I(0) = I_0, \quad V(0) = V_0, \quad t \in [0, T].$$

In the above system $S(t)$, $I(t)$ and $V(t)$ denote the proportion of the susceptibles, infectives and immune, respectively. μ , γ and β are respectively, birth and death rate, recovery rate and contact rate. It is also considered that k fractions of susceptibles are vaccinated in unite time, and there is no disease acquired immunity. By virtue of the equation

$$(2) \quad S(t) + I(t) + V(t) = 1,$$

the last equation of the system (1) is ignored and the following two dimensional system along with the condition (2) is considered [4]

$$(3) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{dS}{dt} &= \mu - (\mu + k)S - \beta SI + \gamma I, \\ \frac{dI}{dt} &= \beta SI - (\mu + \gamma)I, \end{aligned}$$

$$S(0) = S_0, \quad I(0) = I_0, \quad t \in [0, T].$$

In this paper, we present a new method for solving the above SIV model. The method is based on the Ritz-Galerkin technique.

1. SOLVING THE SIV MODEL BY THE RITZ-GALERKIN METHOD

Since in our subsequent development, we use Legendre polynomials for approximating functions, in the first we state some basic properties of these polynomials. Of course, it is possible to use other types of polynomials for approximations such as Taylor, Bernstein, etc.

The Legendre polynomials are orthogonal polynomials on the interval $[-1, 1]$ and can be determined with the following recurrence formula

$$L_{i+1}(y) = \frac{2i+1}{i+1}yL_i(y) - \frac{i}{i+1}L_{i-1}(y), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots$$

where $L_0(y) = 1$ and $L_1(y) = y$. By change of variable $y = \frac{2x}{T} - 1$ we will have Legendre polynomials $p_m(x)$ of order $m \geq 1$ which are defined on the interval $[0, T]$, and can be determined with the following recurrence formula:

$$p_{m+1}(x) = \frac{2m+1}{m+1} \left(\frac{2x}{T} - 1 \right) p_m(x) - \frac{m}{m+1} p_{m-1}(x), \quad m = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

$$p_0(x) = 1, \quad p_1(x) = \frac{2x}{T} - 1.$$

Let $H = L^2[0, T]$ and for $m \in \mathbb{N} \cup p\{0\}$, $\{p_0, p_1, \dots, p_m\} \subset H$ is the set of Legendre polynomials, $Y = \text{Span}\{p_0, p_1, \dots, p_m\}$, and f be an arbitrary element in H . Since Y is a finite dimensional vector space, f has the unique best approximation out of Y such as $y_0 \in Y$, that is

$$\exists y_0 \in Y; \quad \forall y \in Y \|f - y_0\|_2 \leq \|f - y\|_2,$$

where $\|f\|_2 = \sqrt{\langle f, f \rangle}$. Since $y_0 \in Y$, there exist the unique coefficients $c_j, j = 0, \dots, m$ such that, $f(x) \simeq y_0 = \sum_{j=0}^m c_j p_j$, where c_j can be calculated from $c_j = \frac{\langle f(x), p_j(x) \rangle}{\langle p_j(x), p_j(x) \rangle}$.

We consider the following theorem.

[13] Let $f \in C[0, T]$, then there exist a sequence of polynomials $p_n(t)$ that converges uniformly to $f(t)$ on $[0, T]$.

Suppose $C^1[0, T]$ be the space of functions with continuous derivative on the interval $[0, T]$ equipped with the norm $\|\cdot\|_1$ where

$$\forall f \in C^1[0, T], \quad \|f\|_1 = \|f\|_\infty + \|f'\|_\infty.$$

The following corollary shows that for each function in the Banach space $C^1[0, 1]$, there exists a sequence of approximating polynomials in which each polynomial of the sequence satisfies the initial condition of the function.

Let $f(t) \in C^1[0, T]$ and $f(0) = f_0$. There exists a sequence of polynomial functions $\{s_l(t)\}_{l \in \mathbb{N}} \subset C^1[0, T]$ such that $s_l \rightarrow f$ with respect to $\|\cdot\|_1$ and for all $l \in \mathbb{N}$, $s_l(0) = f_0$.

We consider vectors $\Psi_n(t)$, $C_{n,m}^i$ and expansions $\tilde{S}_{n,m}$, $\tilde{I}_{n,m}$ and $\tilde{V}_{n,m}$ as follows.

$$\Psi_n(t) = \begin{bmatrix} p_0(t)t \\ \vdots \\ p_n(t)t \end{bmatrix}, \quad C_{n,m}^i = \begin{bmatrix} c_{0,m}^i \\ \vdots \\ c_{n,m}^i \end{bmatrix}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \quad m, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+,$$

$$(4) \quad \begin{aligned} \tilde{S}_{n,m}(t) &= C_{n,m}^1 \cdot \Psi_n(t) + \sqrt{S_0}, \\ \tilde{I}_{n,m}(t) &= C_{n,m}^2 \cdot \Psi_n(t) + \sqrt{I_0}, \\ \tilde{V}_{n,m}(t) &= C_{n,m}^3 \cdot \Psi_n(t) + \sqrt{V_0}. \end{aligned}$$

Assume that

$$(5) \quad \begin{aligned} E_1(t) &= 2\tilde{S}_{n,m} \frac{d\tilde{S}_{n,m}}{dt} - \mu + (\mu + k)\tilde{S}_{n,m}^2(t) + \beta\tilde{S}_{n,m}^2(t)\tilde{I}_{n,m}^2(t) - \gamma\tilde{I}_{n,m}^2(t), \\ E_2(t) &= 2\tilde{I}_{n,m} \frac{d\tilde{I}_{n,m}}{dt} - \beta\tilde{S}_{n,m}^2(t)\tilde{I}_{n,m}^2(t) + (\mu + \gamma)\tilde{I}_{n,m}^2(t), \\ E_3(t) &= \tilde{S}_{n,m}^2(t) + \tilde{I}_{n,m}^2(t) + \tilde{V}_{n,m}^2(t) - 1. \end{aligned}$$

Using Gaussian quadrature formula [14] to approximate integration

$$\int_0^T E_i(t)p_j(t)dt.$$

For $i = 1, 2, 3$ and $j = 0, \dots, n$, we have

$$(6) \quad A_{i,j} = \frac{T}{2} \sum_{q=0}^m w_q E_i\left(T\left(\frac{\tau_q}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)\right) \cdot p_j\left(T\left(\frac{\tau_q}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right)\right),$$

where τ_q , $q = 0, \dots, m$ are $m + 1$ zeros of Legendre polynomial L_{m+1} and w_q are the corresponding weights [14]. Solving the following system of $(3n + 3)$ equations and unknowns

$$(7) \quad A_{i,j} = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \quad j = 0, \dots, n,$$

values of $c_{j,m}^i$, for $i = 1, 2, 3$ and $j = 0, \dots, n$ can be achieved. Substituting $c_{j,m}^i$'s in (4) the following approximate solution for the SIV system (3) is achieved

$$(8) \quad S_{n,m}(t) = \tilde{S}_{n,m}^2(t), \quad I_{n,m}(t) = \tilde{I}_{n,m}^2(t), \quad V_{n,m}(t) = \tilde{V}_{n,m}^2(t),$$

where

$$S_{n,m}(0) = S_0, \quad I_{n,m}(0) = I_0, \quad V_{n,m}(0) = V_0.$$

2. ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

In this section, we apply the method presented in Section 2 to solve the following test examples.

In the current example, we consider the initial proportion of susceptibles, infectives and immune respectively as $S_0 = I_0 = V_0 = \frac{1}{3}$, in a community also for epidemic parameters let $\mu = \frac{1}{70}$, $\gamma = \frac{1}{10}$, $k = 0.05$, $\beta = 0.1$ [4] and $T = 5$ in the system (3).

Using the method presented in Section 2 with $n = 8$ and $m = 10$ in (4) we obtain approximate solutions $S_{8,10}$, $I_{8,10}$ and $V_{8,10}$, by solving system (7) and considering (8).

In Figure 1 graphs of $S_{8,10}$, $I_{8,10}$ and $V_{8,10}$ are plotted respectively from left to right. Figure 1 shows the approximate change of the proportion of susceptibles, infectives and immune during the time period $[0, 5]$. For instance, we achieve the proportion of susceptibles, infectives and immune respectively, 0.366104, 0.2629 and 0.370996 at time $t = 3$. Figure 2 shows the following absolute errors

$$\begin{aligned} E_1(t) &= \frac{dS_{8,10}}{dt} - \frac{1}{70} + \left(\frac{1}{70} + 0.05\right)S_{8,10}(t) + \frac{S_{8,10}(t)I_{8,10}(t)}{10} - \frac{I_{8,10}(t)}{10}, \\ E_2(t) &= \frac{dI_{8,10}}{dt} - \frac{S_{8,10}(t)I_{8,10}(t)}{10} + \left(\frac{1}{70} + \frac{1}{10}\right)I_{8,10}(t), \\ E_3(t) &= S_{8,10}(t) + I_{8,10}(t) + V_{8,10}(t) - 1. \end{aligned}$$

According to the model, the vaccination rate is the fraction of susceptibles who are vaccinated in the unite time. The results show that after the time t , the proportion of infective people is less than the proportion of susceptible individuals and the proportion of immune individuals in the community. Graphs in Figure 1 also show that with the spread of the epidemic in the community the proportions of susceptibles and immune are increasing during the time period while the proportion of infectives decreases.

Let $k = 0.05$, $\beta = \frac{1}{3}$, $S_0 = 0.82$, $I_0 = 0.13$, $V_0 = 0.05$, $\mu = \frac{1}{70}$, $\gamma = \frac{1}{10}$ [4] and $T = 5$ with $n = 8$ and $m = 10$. We obtain approximate solution $S_{8,10}$, $I_{8,10}$ and $V_{8,10}$ with the following absolute error.

Figure 1: Approximate proportion of susceptibles $S_{8,10}$, infectives $I_{8,10}$ and immune $V_{8,10}$ in example 1.

Figure 2: Absolute errors $E_1(t)$, $E_2(t)$ and $E_3(t)$ of example 1 respectively from left to right.

$$E_1(t) = \frac{dS_{8,10}}{dt} - \frac{1}{70} + \left(\frac{1}{70} + 0.05\right)S_{8,10}(t) + \frac{S_{8,10}(t)I_{8,10}(t)}{3} - \frac{I_{8,10}(t)}{10},$$

$$E_2(t) = \frac{dI_{8,10}}{dt} - \frac{S_{8,10}(t)I_{8,10}(t)}{3} + \left(\frac{1}{70} + \frac{1}{10}\right)I_{8,10}(t),$$

$$E_3(t) = S_{8,10}(t) + I_{8,10}(t) + V_{8,10}(t) - 1.$$

Figures 3 and 4 show the plot of the results of this example. The results obtained in examples 1 and 2 show that for different parameters in the model with only

Figure 3: Approximate proportion of susceptibles $S_{8,10}$, infectives $I_{8,10}$ and immune $V_{8,10}$ in example 2.

Figure 4: Absolute errors $E_1(t)$, $E_2(t)$ and $E_3(t)$ of example 2 respectively from left to right.

a few approximations, a satisfactory result is achieved using the method presented in this paper. With the aid of the obtained approximate solutions for the model, we can estimate the proportion of the people in any state in the community and observe the influence of the vaccination on the spread of the disease and control of the epidemic in the community.

3. CONCLUSION

The Ritz-Galerkin method for solving the SIV model is utilized. This way Legendre orthogonal polynomials and Gauss quadrature formulas are used to reduce the SIV system of differential equations to the problem of solving algebraic equations. The method has the property that preserving the initial conditions of the system. Illustrative examples are included to demonstrate the efficiency of the method. In test problems, it is shown that the method gives satisfactory results with only a few approximations.

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